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Sustainability Transition Assessment and Research of Bio-based Products

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communication, dissemination
and publication activities

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Preface

Communication, dissemination and publication activities are key elements within STAR-ProBio. A special effort has been made during the first year of the project to ensure these activities are properly developed, implemented and managed. These activities follow the guidelines established in the Communication and Dissemination Strategy developed in the starting phase of the project within Work Package 10 (WP10) "Knowledge transfer, training and dissemination".

Progress towards objectives

Communication, dissemination and publication activities developed and completed during the first year of STAR-ProBio fulfilled the objectives established by the Communication and Dissemination Strategy, reaching out a large range of stakeholders and contributing to the further exploitation of the project results within key stakeholders and relevant communities.

Achievements and current status

Deliverable achieved on time. All communication, dissemination and publication activities planned for the first year of STAR-ProBio were successfully achieved.

Summary

Communication, dissemination and publication activities play a vital role within STAR-ProBio. The first year report on these activities lists activities carried out in all Work Packages during the period May 2017 – April 2018. These activities include framework activities for the whole project such as the establishment of a brand identity and ICT channels, and the elaboration of a Data Management Plan, and specific communication and dissemination activities such as interviews, surveys, workshops, webinars, meetings, scientific and general publications, etc. The report describes for all these activities the target groups reached and messages delivered. Finally, the report also includes an indicative list of expected communication, dissemination and publication activities for the second year of the project (May 2018 – April 2019).

1 Objective

STAR-ProBio has concluded its first year of activities developing sustainability assessment tools for bio-based products. The main goal of communication, dissemination and publication activities is to reach out to the widest possible range of stakeholders to promote further exploitation of the project results within key stakeholders and relevant communities. Communication, dissemination and publication activities aim at ensuring that the results gained during the course of the STAR-ProBio project exert their full impact in a coordinated and resource efficient way, and in synergy with the activities of the different Work Packages.

The specific objectives of communication, dissemination and publication activities are:

- Create a brand identity and dedicated dissemination channels for the project;
- Build and maintain professional and collaborative relationship with stakeholders;
- Transfer effectively knowledge developed by STAR-ProBio through the organisation of workshops and events;
- Publish results of STAR-ProBio in open access publications and dedicated blogs;
- Share regularly information through a dedicated website and social media;
- Make available sustainability assessment tools, examples and case studies developed by STAR-ProBio

The first year report on communication, dissemination and publication activities lists and describes the concrete activities carried out during the period May 2017 – April 2018 and presents an indicative list of expected activities for the second year of project operation.

2 Responsibilities within the project

2.1 CoDNOC

On June 20th 2017, Louise Summerton (University of York) was appointed by the leader of WP10 as the Communication, Dissemination, Networking and Outreach Coordinator (CoDNOC) for STAR-ProBio.

Responsibilities of the CoDNOC include the supervision of the formulation of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy, as well as the creation of a brand identity including the STAR-ProBio logo and templates for website, dissemination and training documents and presentations. During the first year of operations, the CODNOC has ensured that all resources, including the website, flyers, posters, presentation slides and promotional banners have a professional and uniform look. Her activities as CoDNOC have been supported by the team of SQ Consult and have covered the following:

- Coordination, organisation and monitoring of all dissemination activities;
- Encouraging partners to initiate and to participate;
- Ensuring regular quality content for the various dissemination channels and activities.

The CoDNOC has performed a final check to ensure all materials produced by major activities before their external distribution took place.

2.2 Coordinator, Executive Board and Work Package leaders

During the first year of the project, the STAR-ProBio Coordinator and the Executive Board¹ have been responsible for the formulation of all key messages of the project, always in coordination with the CoDNOC. The Coordinator and the Executive Board have complied with their responsibility for the approval of those major communication and dissemination activities that involve results of more than one work package. Major activities that involve results of only one work package were approved by the respective work package leader.

Work Package leaders took on their responsibility for the correct implementation of all communication and dissemination activities planned and implemented within their work package. These activities were timely informed to the CoDNOC.

SQ Consult as the leader of WP10 performed the following responsibilities during the first year of activities:

- Appointment of the STAR-ProBio's CoDNOC;
- Monitoring all communication and dissemination activities within STAR-ProBio;
- Organisation of the first annual conference of STAR-ProBio;
- Reaching out and establish working contacts with relevant stakeholders.

¹ The Executive Board is integrated by all work Package leaders

3 Brand identity and dissemination channels

The overarching objective of the established STAR-ProBio brand identity is authenticating and strengthening the communication and dissemination of STAR-ProBio's messages. Our brand identity ensures that all communication and dissemination products, including reports, the website, flyers, posters, presentation slides and promotional banners have a professional and uniform look. Our brand identity also greatly facilitates recognition by stakeholders who cross paths with any of the project's outputs more than once.

3.1 Logo

The core element of the project's visual identity is the STAR-ProBio logo. The visual identity authenticates and strengthens the communication and dissemination of STAR-ProBio's messages. The visual identity ensures that all communication and dissemination products, including reports, the website, flyers, posters, presentation slides and promotional banners have a professional and uniform look. STAR-ProBio's logo is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: STAR-ProBio Logo

3.1.1 Logo development

An intra-consortium consultation during the month after the project kick-off resulted in the submission of 12 logo proposals (of which several with multiple variations of the same basic concept) for STAR-ProBio. A project committee formed by the Project Coordinator, the CoDNOC and WP10 team representatives narrowed the options down to a shortlist of 3 logo options, on which all consortium partners could vote until early July 2017. The logo finally selected by the partners, Figure 1, was kindly designed by Vignesh Gopal of Edon Design.

3.1.2 Logo implementation

Substantial effort has been made to ensure that the logo is taken up wherever relevant, including all project templates, posters, promotional material, website and social media. All partners have been instructed how and when to use the logo via email and at the Month 06 general assembly.

STAR-ProBio partners have made considerable effort in adopting the STAR-ProBio logo and brand identity, not only in formal deliverables but also through the consistent use of the document templates described below, the use of the logo in internal and external presentations and documents, web articles, email signatures etc. and the STAR-ProBio promotional tote bags, notebooks, banners and posters used at communication and dissemination events (Figure 2).

Figure 2: STAR-ProBio branded promotional material: Tote bag and notebook with a pen, made from sustainable resources

3.2 Templates

Templates for different uses applying the STAR-ProBio brand identity were developed and distributed for mandatory use within the consortium in Month 05 (September 2017) of the project. All templates were created from scratch, but experience from several partners in other Horizon 2020 and similar projects were taken into account in their development. Testing by WP10 team members was followed by a final round of review by all project partners. These templates include:

- Report, as applied to this communication and dissemination report;
- Headed paper, for letters, memorandums, meeting minutes and other short documents;

- PowerPoint presentation, including title, content and acknowledgment slides;
- Excel figures and colour scheme, to be applied in charts and visuals;
- Business cards.

Screenshots of the various templates are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: STAR-ProBio templates

All communication and dissemination templates include the STAR-ProBio logo and the acknowledgement of EU funding given through the Horizon2020 programme.

3.3 Website

The STAR-ProBio website <http://www.star-probio.eu/> is the main channel for dissemination of project information. The STAR-ProBio domain has been registered on the 21st of April 2017 and since then content has been uploaded; maintenance will be continuous until the end of project and will subsequently remain active for up to five years after the end of the project. The website is designed in such a way that it meets the communication and dissemination needs of wide range of users. The website was built with the following characteristics:

- Attractive to the different target groups;
- User-friendly;
- Interactive.

A screenshot of the STAR-ProBio website homepage is included below in Figure 4.

Figure 4: STAR-ProBio website homepage

3.3.1 Website sections

The website serves as a knowledge platform for the target audiences and as a place to provide access to reports and freely available publications, case studies, STAR-ProBio news and networks. The STAR-ProBio website has two distinct areas (public and private) each aimed at a different audience:

- **Public area** – Keeps the interested parties accessing the website informed on the project and its development. Its aim is not only to inform but rather to encourage engagement of people by allowing easy access to extensive information about STAR-ProBio and its activities including background information, news and events announcements, articles alerts, contact details, etc. It makes the public project deliverables available as well as the published materials the project has created. The public area of the website has the following subsections: “home page”, “objectives”, “WPs”, “deliverables”, “partners”, “news” and “contact us”.
- **Private area** - Designed as a single working platform for partners, External Advisory Board members and key stakeholders. Moreover, the private area is used to share confidential documents. Access to private area requires a login procedure. All partners have been assigned with credentials (user id and password). The private area of the website is intended to support the general workflow by allowing smooth communication between project partners and serves the needs of the internal communication by distributing different sorts of documents and sets of documents. The private area hosts the STAR-ProBio Online library. The STAR-ProBio Online Library hosts

(scientific) publications and other information (deliverables) on all project activities that are open for access/download by the external users of the website. All consortium members are able to upload files in the Online library.

3.3.2 Website languages

The main sections of the websites are available in:

- English
- German
- French
- Italian
- Polish

3.3.3 Website content

The website includes general information about the project, consortium and guidance on how to use project outcomes. Specific functions of the website which pertain to dissemination include:

Currently operational

- Online STAR-ProBio newsletter (full text archive) with online subscription;
- Cross-links to other key related projects, e.g. BioCannDo, BioLinX Project, BIOPEN, BioWays, CommBeBiz, InnProBIO, Pilots4U, ProBIO, RoadToBio, STAR4BBI;
- Information on STAR-ProBio workshops and conferences. For these events, an internal area to collect comments and feedback from stakeholders will be set up;
- News items about the project:
 - APRIL 12, 2018 - UWM Internal Seminar
 - MARCH 8, 2018 - STAR-ProBio Workshop at the Climate Show 2018
 - FEBRUARY 12, 2018 - STAR-ProBio on BIOWATCH
 - FEBRUARY 1, 2018 - First STAR-ProBio Focus Group Webinar
 - DECEMBER 20, 2017 - 1st Newsletter, December 2017
 - NOVEMBER 27, 2017 - STAR-ProBio @BBI JU Stakeholder Forum 2017, Bruxelles
 - NOVEMBER 27, 2017 - Bio Challenge!
 - NOVEMBER 23, 2017 - STAR-ProBio @Maker Faire Rome
 - OCTOBER 27, 2017 - 1st Meeting of the General Assembly, Rome - 19-20/10/2017
 - SEPTEMBER 18, 2017 - 1st internal workshop "Principles, criteria and indicators for sustainability transition assessment to circular and bio-based economy"
 - JULY 31, 2017 - #BLOG_Production, use, and fate of all plastics ever made
 - JUNE 26, 2017 - #BLOG_Coordinators Day, Brussels, 22 June 2017
 - JUNE 19, 2017 - Kick-off Meeting
 - APRIL 21, 2017 - STAR-ProBio launched!

Foreseen:

- Information on the STAR-ProBio case studies;

- Online background and training material;
- Online access to the main tools/applications developed in the project, explaining their background and how to use them, including link to the web based interactive tool.

3.3.4 Website statistics

The total number of visits to the STAR-ProBio website since the beginning (May 1st, 2017 - April 23rd, 2018) is 3.078. The geographic origin of the visitors, if known:

- Italy: 1.229
- Germany: 317
- Spain: 221
- United Kingdom: 170
- Belgium: 161
- Others: 980

The average number of website visits per day has been increasing. A recent sample of the traffic statistics of the STAR-ProBio website for the time-frame January 1st, 2018 - April 23rd, 2018 recorded 1.471 site visits. The origin, website sub-sections and the path users took between sections are shown in Figure 5: 45% of traffic comes to the website directly, 38% through Google, 7% through Twitter and the remaining 10% through links on other websites. Just over half the traffic starts on the home page, 42% of total traffic visits more than one of the website sections and 24% visits more than 2 sections. After the homepage, the News and Member sections are the most popular.

Figure 5: STAR-ProBio web traffic analysis 01/01/2018 to 23/04/2018

3.3.5 Website Responsibility

Unitelma Sapienza administers the website and takes care of its technical set up and maintenance, analysing periodically the website traffic through Google Analytics in order to measure how users interact with the website content.

A dedicated staff member updates the website regularly, sharing news, information on events, presentations and relevant studies. Content management is the responsibility of the Project Coordinator [UNITELMA], the CoDNOC and WP leaders.

The CoDNOC makes sure that all information and knowledge generated in the project are widely circulated among the participants. In the internal area of the website, the posting of documents encourages knowledge exchange.

The website is regularly updated by placing interesting items on the home page not only to keep the audience informed but also to raise continued interest of already attracted visitors.

3.4 Social media channels

Social media platforms provide an important opportunity to engage with stakeholders and the general public. As a fundamental part of its communication strategy, the STAR-ProBio project actively maintains profiles on social media.

The primary project social media channels are:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/star-probio-655816145>
The profile was created soon after the project started. A screenshot of the LinkedIn profile page is presented below in Figure 6;

STAR-ProBio – a multi-actor collaborative Research and Innovation Action (RIA) coordinated by Unitelma Sapienza University and including 15 partners from 11 European countries – has been awarded three-year Horizon 2020 funding.

Figure 6: Screenshot of STAR-ProBio's LinkedIn profile page

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/STAR-ProBio-343691609383137/>
The profile was created soon after the project started. A screenshot of the Facebook profile page is presented below in Figure 7;

Figure 7: Screenshot of STAR-ProBio’s Facebook profile page

- Twitter: https://twitter.com/STAR_ProBio
The profile was created soon after the project started. A screenshot of the project’s twitter account profile page is presented below in Figure 8;

Figure 8: Screenshot of STAR-ProBio’s Twitter profile page

The current status of these accounts is represented in Table 1 (figures provided as of 23/04/2018):

Table 1: Current (23/04/2018) status of STAR-ProBio social media networks

	Network	Content
LinkedIn	323 Members; 331 Followers	30 Posts
Twitter	189 Followers; 312 Followed	77 Tweets; 72 Likes
Facebook	105 Followers	43 Posts; 102 Likes

4 Data Management Plan (DMP)

A Data Management Plan (DMP) for data generated and/or collected during the project was completed in month 06 (October 2017). It provides guidance to the consortium on identifying and disseminating data and knowledge gathered in the project, not restricted to the formal project deliverables. Key examples are databases and inventories of collected information underlying the project deliverables and the supporting data for scientific manuscripts.

Due to the interdisciplinary nature of the project, there has been and will be a wide range of types of data generated: (1) environmental sustainability assessment performed in WPs 2 and 3 (and to some extent in WP 7) is expected to generate raw empirical data and measurements; (2) economic and social sustainability assessment performed in WPs 4, 5 and 6 will include survey data where confidentiality must be respected; (3) literature reviews on existing data have been carried out in WPs 1 and 9 (covered in more depth in the WP descriptions).

Datasets generated by STAR-ProBio can be interesting for:

- Members of the scientific community;
- Professionals with a link to bio-based product sustainability;
- Those active in the specific research field to which the dataset contributes;
- Other research projects that can continue to build on or combine their work with STAR-ProBio datasets.

The project is aiming to make as much of its findings and output available to the public, ensuring it's easy to find and remains available after the project ends. The default approach is to make fully finalized datasets publicly available, unless there is a clear reason not to. At the time of writing this report (April 2018) the first datasets have been made available in the project website. In addition to uploading data sets to the project website, STAR-ProBio has chosen the Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>) repository for making datasets publicly available. For some disciplines, datasets are more likely to be found by potential users if deposited in a repository which is specific to the discipline. Therefore for each dataset the [Registry of Research data Repositories](#) (www.re3data.org) should be consulted, in order to determine most appropriate repository.

In order to ensure continuity across the project, certain standards are set out in the DMP. For instance, fieldwork requires standardisation of questionnaires, interview structures and other means of obtaining personalised information. All data published is subject to an internal peer-review process prior to publication. With STAR-ProBio being a trans-disciplinary project across several WPs, the vast majority of the data generated will be fed directly back into the project to ensure an effective cross-fertilisation among WPs. As STAR-ProBio has opted to take part in the Open Research Data Pilot, much of the data publication is and will continue to be done via the website to ensure full internal dissemination, whilst simultaneously making it publicly available. However, this is subject to individual cases review as, by nature of having commercial partners, some data releases may also reveal confidential information. The Project Management Committee (PMC) is responsible to constantly review this strategy and as such it forms a main task and set of deliverables in WP10.

The dissemination of this data is foreseen to go beyond the lifespan of the project. As such, the website will remain available for at least 5 years after the formal project end date and a link to the STAR-ProBio webpage will be established in all the partners and advisory board members' webpages and also in other relevant websites.

6 Publications

The scientific community is one of the main target groups of STAR-ProBio. According to STAR-ProBio's Communication and Dissemination Strategy, the research teams will aim to publish a minimum of 8 scientific papers in journals during the project lifetime. These publications should aim at a high impact factor.

Three scientific publications have been produced in the first year of activities of the project: Two journal papers and one book chapter. These scientific publications have focused on analysis and findings from WPs 1, 2 and 6. These scientific publications are meant not only to specialists in bioeconomy and bioproducts, but also on scientists in any other disciplines that could in one or another way benefit from STAR-ProBio outcomes.

Journal papers

- P. Gullón, B. Gullón, I. Dávila, J. Labidi, S. Gonzalez-Garcia, **Comparative environmental Life Cycle Assessment of integral revalorization of vine shoots from a biorefinery perspective**, *Sci Total Environ.*, 2017, 624, 225; DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.12.036>; Written by Universidade de Santiago de Compostela relevant to the work of WP2.
- P.M. Falcone & E. Imbert, **Social Life Cycle Approach as a Tool for Promoting the Market Uptake of Bio-Based Products from a Consumer Perspective**, *Sustainability*, 2018, 10(4), 1031; doi:10.3390/su10041031; Open access; Written by Unitelma Sapienza relevant to the work of WP6.

Book chapter

- P.M. Falcone, S. Fumagalli, E. Imbert, C. Imbriani, P. Morone, S. Trenti, **Recenti sviluppi della bioeconomia in Italia: un driver di sviluppo per il Mezzogiorno?** In *Rapporto Svimez 2017 sull'economia del Mezzogiorno*, Publisher: Società Editrice il Mulino P.M. Falcone, S. Fumagalli, E. Imbert, C. Imbriani, P. Morone, S. Trenti Pages: 547 - 565, ISBN: 978-88-15-27354-3 URL: <https://www.mulino.it/isbn/9788815273543>. Book chapter written by Unitelma Sapienza relevant to the work of WP1. Includes a section entitled - A New Challenge for Europe: Standard and Label for Bioproducts - which provides a review of the state of the art in defining standards for bio-based products.

STAR-ProBio partners have also published seven non-scientific publications, mainly in electronic magazines and other web platforms. These non-scientific publications aim at disseminating project information and news to policy makers, business stakeholders, public procurers, certification bodies, researchers, students, political stakeholders and general public.

- **Dzisiaj odpad-jutro surowiec (Today waste-tomorrow raw material)**, published by partner UWM in the University Magazine, edition August – September 2017. Available at http://www.uwm.edu.pl/sites/default/files/wiad-uniwer/2017/wu-2017-08_09.pdf

- **STAR-ProBio – General Assembly**, published as e-article in the website of ECOS on 31/10/2017. Available at <http://ecostandard.org/star-probio-general-assembly/>
- **Erste Ergebnisse aus dem Europäischen Forschungsprojekt STAR-ProBio**, published by partner TUB in DIN Mitteilungen January 2018 issue.
- **STAR-ProBio BBI-JU SEED** through the BioWatch dissemination tool of the BIOWAYS project, package information prepared by University of York and published on the Bioways website on 09/02/2018. Available at: <http://library.bioways.eu/SEEDHTML/player.php>
- **Assessment and Survey of Sustainability of Biogenic Products**, published by partner AUA as a press release and article in the AUA website on 02/03/2018. Available at <https://www2.aua.gr/el/news-events/nea/axiologisi-kai-ereyna-metavasis-stin-aeiforia-ton-viogenon-proionton>
- **Beyond LCA: Why Impact Evaluation Strengthens the Business Case for Bio-based Plastics**, website article published by partner Quantis on 03/04/2018. Available at <https://quantis-intl.com/bio-based-plastics/>
- **DIN Mitteilungen:** S. Wurster, L. Ladu, S.Majer. Article on the results and interim results of WPs 1, 5 and 9. Förderung biobasierter Produkte durch Normung und Zertifizierung. Horizon-2020-Projekt STAR-ProBio. Bisher Erreichtes, Handlungsbedarf und Lösungsansätze. DIN Mitteilungen April 2018, 13-21

7 Focus groups, symposia, forums and other events

Partners of STAR-ProBio have organised 4 events (2 workshops, 2 focus group) and participated in 10 more (8 oral presentations and 2 panel discussions in symposia) during the first year of STAR-ProBio. According to STAR-ProBio's Communication and Dissemination Strategy, the research teams will aim to participate and present in at least 6 international conferences and trade fairs. Team members also attended 3 specialised seminars relevant to STAR-ProBio's research. All these activities are summarised in Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4. The respective dissemination forms with all detailed information of these activities are presented in Annex 1.

All the events organised by STAR-ProBio have adopted a cooperative approach, promoting active exchange with experts invited. Presentations and panel debates in which STAR-ProBio members have participated were carefully prepared to address a varied audience including industry representatives, legislators and policy makers, standardisation and certification professionals, environmental NGOs and the scientific community in general.

Messages transferred in all these events have been elaborated to contribute to:

- The development of efficient, implementable and fit-for-purpose sustainability schemes and criteria and indicators and contribute achieving the objectives of policies related to the bio-based economy.
- The development of objective and quality life cycle assessments based on robust and agreed methods.
- Ensure market pull for bio-based products.

Table 2: Internal workshops and experts focus groups organised by partners in the first year of STAR-ProBio

N°	Title	Date/place	Audience	Partners involved	Further details
1	Principles, criteria and indicators for sustainability transition assessment to circular and bio-based economy	15/09/2017 Olsztyn, Poland	15 Polish researchers	UWM	First internal workshop organised by UWM summarising current work on WPs 1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 9 and 10
2	Gap analyses of existing sustainability schemes and technical standards, web-conference organised by WP1	26/10/2017 Web-based event streamlined by DBFZ from Berlin, Germany	19 experts from partners and external parties discussed topics	DBFZ TUB SQ Consult	The experts discussion aimed at analysing identified gaps and analysing possible synergies among schemes and standards
3	Sustainability Assessment Factors for Bio-Based Products, Web-based focus group event organised by WP5	29/01/2018 Web-based event streamlined by TUB from Berlin, Germany	More than 20 experts including project partners and public procurers, businesses, business associations, research, standardisation and certification and NGOs	TUB UNITELMA SQ Consult ECOS	Luana Ladu (TU Berlin) moderated the Focus group in which key market players were asked about key criteria and indicators for sustainability assessments schemes applied to bio-based products.
4	Sustainability Transition Assessment and Research of Bio-based Products: Progression and Shortcomings of Current Sustainability Standards of Bio-based Products	22/03/2018 Olsztyn, Poland	20 Polish researchers	UWM	Second internal workshop organised by UWM summarising current work on WPs 1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 9 and 10

Table 3: Participation with oral presentations and panel discussions in specialised events during the first year of STAR-ProBio

N°	Title	Date/place	Audience	Partners involved	Further details
1	"STAR-ProBio" in the H2020 Coordinators Day	22/06/2017 Brussels, Belgium	Coordinators of European projects and Officers of the European Commission. Over 100 EU participants	Unitelma TUB	Luana Ladu (TUB) and Francesca Govoni (Unitelma) presented. STAR-ProBio to officers of the European Commission as well as coordinators of other similar projects. This was also a great opportunity to liaise with other projects with overlapping interests.
2	"The Bio-Economy and the transition towards circular Economy - Sustainability schemes, standards, labels and certification of biobased products" in the 50 th Int. Seminars on Planetary Emergencies	21/08/2017 Erice, Sicily, Italy	Scientists, researchers, policy makers About 100 global participants from Europe, Asia, Americas and Africa	University of Bologna	Diego Marazza presented the STAR-ProBio project. As a direct consequence he invited Prof. Carmine di Figlio to join the Advisory Board.
3	"Biorefinery processes in circular economy" in the workshop – BioBIGG, State of play of bio-economy in the South Baltic Area	06/12/2017 Gdansk, Poland	Scientists, researchers, students, ecologists About 40 EU participants.	UWM	Presentation by Janusz Gołaszewski
4	"Bridging the gaps for a 'circular' bio-economy: selection criteria, bio-based value chain and stakeholder mapping" in the ECO-BIO Challenges in Building a Sustainable Biobased Economy 2018 Conference	4/03/2018-7/03/2018 Dublin, Ireland	Scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students. About 250 global participants	U. of York TUB	Kadam Lokesh (University of York) presented outputs from WP1
5	"Forecasting innovations and technological trends in the European bio-based industry: Experts view and patent analysis" in the ECO-BIO Challenges in	4/03/2018-7/03/2018 Dublin,	Scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students. About 250 global	TUB (Luana Ladu)	Luana Ladu (TUB) presented results from STAR-ProBio and the STAR4BBI projects

	Building a Sustainable Biobased Economy 2018 Conference	Ireland	participants		
6	"How can we shape circular bio-economy in a multi-level perspective?" in the 3 rd edition of the NEST-conference, "New frontiers in sustainability transitions"	15/03/2018-16/03/2018 Utrecht, The Netherlands	PhD students and ECRs, senior researchers	Unitelma	Valentina Tartiu presented findings of the project
7	"Presentation of STAR-ProBio" in the Mutual learning workshop: Maximizing collaboration among EC funded projects communicating about Bioeconomy	28/03/2018 Brussels, Belgium.	Representatives from 23 H2020 projects and EC policy officers	ECOS	Mathilde Crépy presented the project. Event organised by the Biovoices consortium
8	"Innovation in the bioeconomy: overcoming barriers for sustainable bio-based products & biofuels" in the final event of the European Research and Innovation project ButaNext	12/04/2018 Brussels, Belgium	Scientists, researchers, industries, NGOs & policy makers, ca. 80 people from across Europe.	ECOS SQ Consult	Mathilde Crépy (ECOS) joined the 1-hour panel discussion on market barriers. Next to the panel discussion, a poster session took place with ECOS and SQ Consult representation
9	Panellist at the FAO international workshop – Measuring the sustainability of the bioeconomy: Where do we stand/What gaps/What next?	17/04/2018-18/04/2018 Berlin, Germany	42 scientists, researchers, policy makers from across the world	UNITELMA TUB	Piergiuseppe Morone (UNITELMA) and Luana Ladu (TUB) participated in the central panel discussion of the workshop and presented the projects and the gap analysis conducted in WP1
10	"Gaps in sustainability tools and schemes for bio-based products and stakeholders preferences and expectations" in the Conference: Governing sustainability of bioenergy, biomaterial and bioproduct supply chains from forest and agricultural landscapes, organised by IEA Bioenergy Task 43: Biomass Feedstocks for Energy Markets	17/04/2018-19/04/2018 Copenhagen, Denmark,	Researchers, producers of biomass for bioenergy, bio-chemicals and biomaterials, and other stakeholders from the forest, agriculture, biogas and bioenergy sectors. About 100 global	SQ Consult DBFZ TUB	Sergio Ugarte (SQ Consult) presented results from WPs 1, 5 and 9

			participants		
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Table 4: Attendance by STAR-ProBio team members to specialised seminars

N°	Title	Date/place	Audience	Partners involved	Further details
1	Life Cycle Assessment and waste management: theory and practice, seminar delivered by Carlo Ingrao	27/09/2017 Rome, Italy	Five members of UNITELMA	UNITELMA	NA
2	12th European Bioplastics Conference 2017 in Berlin	28/11/2017- 29/11/2017	One member TUB	TUB	Attendance due to relevant topics and networking for the project
3	Empirical Research Avenues for Regional Policy Elaboration, seminar delivered by Marco Capasso	04/12/2017 Rome, Italy	Six members of UNITELMA	UNITELMA	NA

8 Other general dissemination activities

8.1 Electronic newsletter

Two electronic newsletters are planned per year. They are to be distributed by email, published on the website and announced on social media. The [first newsletter](#) was published in December 2017 (Figure 9). Free subscription to the newsletter is possible online via the project website. At the time of writing (April 2018), the newsletter has 93 subscribers.

The target group is all stakeholder groups that may benefit from the outputs and tools produced by STAR-ProBio, the scientific community and interested members of the public at large.

The first newsletter describes the overall project goals and how the individual Work Packages contribute, contains interviews with key researchers, reports on several STAR-ProBio communication and dissemination activities at events and contains an outlook on forthcoming events.

Besides being received by subscribers, the STAR-ProBio partners were asked to forward the newsletter within their network. This way, about 750 stakeholders received it by email. Furthermore, the newsletter was promoted via the STAR-ProBio website and social media. Multiple partners posted about the newsletter on their organisation's website (3 times) and Twitter (4 times), LinkedIn (2 times) and Facebook (1 time).

Figure 9: First newsletter of STAR-ProBio

The second newsletter is scheduled for June 2018. This and future editions will focus more on showcasing recently completed and upcoming project outputs, in order to generate awareness and interest in the knowledge and deliverables produced by the project.

SQ Consult has the overall responsibility for the newsletters. WP leaders are responsible for providing content material and for proposing articles related to the work and findings of their respective Work Packages. Partners can copy the content of different news items and distribute them using their existing communication materials such as their own newsletters, email lists and their websites, as long as the STAR-ProBio Visual Identity is followed (logo and URL).

8.2 Outreach and training materials

Outreach is among the most important aspects of STAR-ProBio's dissemination activities. Outreach and training materials (posters, brochures, leaflets, newsletters, fact sheets, etc.) are used as a means to give visibility to the project and provide relevant information to all publics. All STAR-ProBio outreach and training materials and presentations use the STAR Pro-Bio's logo and templates. The EC logo is shown in all of them and the grant agreement reference is prominently placed.

During the first year of STAR-ProBio activities, partners have produced one podcast and have prepared two exhibitions. The podcast targeted scientists, researchers, students and conservationists mainly. Exhibitions target the same group, but also were meant to inform experts from other projects/initiatives and the general public,

- **Podcast Science behind your Product Choices** published online 16/01/2018, Podcast by Kadam Lokesh, elaborated by University of York for SuperWomenInScience; 276 play-counts at beginning of March 2018. Available at: <https://superwomeninscience.wordpress.com/2018/02/08/elevator-science-part-1/>
- **STAR-ProBio exhibition at the Maker Faire** involving poster, gadgets and a workshop prepared by UNITELMA. Held on 01/12/2017 - 03/12/2017, Rome, Italy. Estimated audience size ca. 110,000 visitors over 3 day event. The Maker Faire is a showcase of invention, creativity, and resourcefulness 'the most important event in the world of innovation'. (<http://www.makerfairerome.eu/en/>)
- **STAR-ProBio exhibition at the BBI Stakeholder Forum** involving PowerPoint presentation, poster and gadgets prepared by UNITELMA and SQ Consult. Held on 06/12/2017 - 07/12/2017, Brussels, Belgium.

8.3 Social media (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook)

STAR-ProBio maintains an active presence three major social media platforms (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook). The main objective is outreach to both stakeholders and the general public, to be findable, recognizable and memorable. Social media are a valuable tool to get STAR-ProBio's existence, key messages and outputs

across to a wide audience and to generate interest in the project and the societal issues that the project aims to alleviate.

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/star-probio-655816145>
LinkedIn is primarily aimed at a professional audience. Members interested in STAR-ProBio can easily follow the project. After the first year, 323 people have joined the project's network and 331 people follow the project through LinkedIn. The 30 entries posted on LinkedIn primarily showcase communication and dissemination events (many of which include photos) which STAR-ProBio is part of, share project news such as the publication of the first newsletter and liking and sharing other related Horizon 2020 projects.

In addition to the project profile on LinkedIn, many STAR-ProBio team members have listed the project on their personal LinkedIn profiles, and several consortium members have shared STAR-ProBio news on their company/institution profile on LinkedIn.

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/STAR-ProBio-343691609383137/>
Facebook is typically used for more informal purposes than LinkedIn, but it helps the user to discover news and information that their friends and liked profiles post. For STAR-ProBio it is therefore an important channel to communicate the project, its aim and outputs to the general public. In the first year, the project's Facebook profile has gathered 105 followers and 102 likes. The profile contains 44 videos and photos, almost exclusively from events in which the project was involved or participated. The 30 posts by the project on Facebook also concentrate on these events, on project outputs such as the first newsletter and relevant related projects industry news. Other projects and people explicitly named SAR-ProBio seven times in their posts. Several of the partners have used their institutional Facebook account to promote STAR-ProBio.

Among the various uses of the STAR-ProBio Facebook account, this platform was used to live stream the first annual STAR-ProBio workshop on 6 April 2018 in Geneva, Switzerland.

- Twitter: https://twitter.com/STAR_ProBio
Twitter is known for its large stream of short messages, which can be spread quickly through the platform, This is particularly useful for news and announcements from the project; posts can reach a large number of people quickly, however older posts don't get much attention. The project's 77 tweets in the first year have generated 72 likes and 189 followers.

Several consortium partners also have used their company/institution Twitter account to share STAR-ProBio information.

9 First annual workshop

On 6th April 2018 the STAR-ProBio project hosted its first international workshop at the Climate Show in Geneva, Switzerland.

A great effort has been put by all fifteen consortium partners to attract the whole range of relevant stakeholders to hear and debate on preliminary findings and future direction of STAR-ProBio. All partners disseminated the invitation and agenda of the workshop through their networks, in particular the GCCE (ca. 300 people, primarily in Europe but some international – mainly academic/industry contacts), the World Food Waste Network (ca. 300 members primarily in Europe but some international, mainly academics working in food waste valorisation – chem, biology, engineers, techno-economic, agricultural science, etc), the Swedish National Agency of (economic) Growth Analysis, Lund University community.

Personalised invitations to 60 relevant stakeholders in Switzerland were made, and an targeted invitation to more than 150 companies and organisations in Europe was sent as well. The newsletter of the project also promoted the workshop.

The workshop was also promoted through STAR-ProBio's ICT channels, mainly the project's social media (Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook) and the STAR-ProBio website, as well as team members' personal profiles in LinkedIn.

The workshop was attended by 53 stakeholders from 15 countries representing a diverse range of backgrounds from research institutions to companies, industry associations and civil society organisations. The 1.5 hour workshop combined presentations on the STAR-ProBio project from Prof. Piergiuseppe Morone of Unitelma Sapienza and on European Standards supporting the market for Bio-based Products from Maria Gustafsson of CEN TC/411 with a panel discussion to explore 'A vision for a bio-based economy: opportunities and challenges for bio-based products'. Chaired by Prof. James of the Green Chemistry Centre of Excellence at the University of York, the panel fostered lively debate and discussion including significant audience participation on three key areas: Policy; Customer acceptability and future markets and Products. Panel members consisted of a complementary blend of industry (including SME), academia, trade association and NGO: Constance Ißbrücker, European Bioplastics; Peter Jürgens, REDcert; José Maria Gómez Palacios, URBIOFIN Project and Biomasa Peninsular S.L.; Enzo Montoneri, University of Torino; Francesco Razza, Novamont and Andreas Taglieber, Firmenich.

Figure 10: Pictures of STAR-ProBio's first annual workshop

The workshop was live-streamed via the STAR-ProBio Facebook page and the recording is still available for viewing via this platform. Feedback from the event was very positive, with 93% of respondents rating the workshop good or excellent with comments including *'the round table was very interesting offering different perspectives'*, *'excellent selection of speakers and management of the discussion, especially engaging participants'*, and *'enjoyed the diversity of participants'* and some helpful suggestions for incorporating in the next event. Afterwards members of the STAR-ProBio Advisory Board continued the discussion over a business lunch.

Workshop Agenda

- **Spotlight on STAR-ProBio** (10 min) – Prof. Piergiuseppe Morone, Project Coordinator, Unitelma Sapienza, IT
 - Aim and objectives of the project
 - Key findings in Year 1
 - Expected future outputs and achievements
- **European Standards supporting the market for Bio-based Products** (15 min) – Solveig Eriksson (CEN/TC 411 representative)
- **Panel Discussion: A vision for a bio-based economy:** Opportunities and challenges for bio-based products (60 mins). Panel members:
 - James Clark, Green Chemistry Centre of Excellence, University of York (Panel convener)
 - Constance Ißbrücker, European Bioplastics
 - Peter Jürgens, REDcert

- José María Gómez Palacios, URBIOFIN Project and Biomasa Peninsular S.L.
- Enzo Montoneri, University of Torino
- Francesco Razza, Novamont
- Andreas Taglieber, Firmenich
- **Next steps and Closing Remarks** (5 mins).

The Full Report on Outcomes of the First Annual Workshop of STAR-ProBio is included in this report as Appendix

10 Expected activities for the second year 1-year period

10.1 Publications

At least 10 scientific publications are planned for the second year of STAR-ProBio. The list of publications is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Expected scientific publications in the second year of STAR-ProBio

Nº	Planned activity	Date	Target Audience	WP Lead	Further Detail
1	Paper for Special Issue of Forest Policy and Economics Journal: "Circular forest bioeconomy - business, economics and sustainability"	30/6/2018	tbc	6	Title: Untangling the different shades of green for the Italian forest-based sector transition towards a circular bioeconomy. (Falcone, P., Tani, A., Tartiu, V.E)
2	Paper for Special Issue of Forest Policy and Economics Journal: "Circular forest bioeconomy - business, economics and sustainability"	30/6/2018	tbc	6, 1 and 5	Title: The role of policy-mix in the transition towards a circular forest bio-based economy (Imbert E., Ladu, L., Morone, P., Quitzow, R.)
3	Paper for special issue of Sustainability journal "Sustainability Transition Towards a Bio-Based Economy: New Technologies, New Products, New Policies"	tbc	tbc	1	Title: Bridging the gaps for a 'circular' bio-economy: selection criteria, bio-based value chain and stakeholder mapping Authors: Kadambari Lokesh, Luana Ladu , Louise Summerton
4	Paper for special issue of Sustainability journal "Sustainability Transition Towards a Bio-Based Economy: New Technologies, New Products, New Policies"	tbc	tbc	9	Title: Gaps and research demand analysis from current certification and standardisation for a sustainable biobased economy (Stefan Majer)
5	Paper in Journal Biofuels, bioproducts and biorefining	Under revision	tbc	2	Title: 'Evaluation of a lignocellulosic biorefinery based on organosolv pulping under a life-cycle assessment approach' (Sara Bello, Carmen Ríos, Gumersindo Feijoo, Maria Teresa Moreira)
6	Planned publication	tbc	tbc	7	Topic: designed policies to oppose ILUC unintended effects in the domain of

					bioeconomy and biobased products
7	Planned publication	tbc	tbc	7	Topic: Land use efficiency indicators for bio-based production
8	Book chapter in Life Cycle Assessment in the Energy System and Sustainable Technologies Sector: Italian experiences.	Accepted for publication	tbc	2	Chapter title: 'Life cycle assessment of renewable energy production from biomass' Authors: Lucia Lijó, Sara González-García, Daniela Lovarelli, Maria Teresa Moreira, Gumersindo Feijoo, Jacopo Bacenetti
9	Book chapter in 'Energy footprint of biorefinery schemes'	Accepted for publication	tbc	2	Chapter title: 'Energy footprint of biorefinery schemes' Authors: Sara Bello, Gumersindo Feijoo, Maria Teresa Moreira
10	Book chapter in Energy Footprint: Industrial Case Studies	Accepted for publication	tbc	2	Chapter title: 'Addressing Environmental Criteria and Energy Footprint in the Selection of Feedstocks for Bioenergy Production' Authors: Iana Salim, Lucía Lijó, Maria Teresa Moreira, Gumersindo Feijoo

At least 2 non-scientific publications are planned for the second year of STAR-ProBio. The list of non-scientific publications is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Expected non-scientific publications in the second year of STAR-ProBio

Nº	Planned activity	Date	Target Audience	WP Lead	Further Detail
1	Article in World Scientific (Richard Ragaini)	tbc	tbc	7	Proceedings of the 50th International Seminars on Planetary Emergencies. STAR-ProBio and reference to the project will be mentioned therein. Expected Aug 2018
2	Article for the newsletter of the Italian network of LCA	tbc	tbc	7	STAR-ProBio and TO-SYNFUEL: two Horizon 2020 projects for the valorisation of bio-based products and residual biomass

10.2 Delphi surveys and roundtable

Delphi surveys and a round table are a core data source in several STAR-ProBio Work Packages and tasks. These activities form a two-way communication with different stakeholders: simultaneously communicate to stakeholders the knowledge and products developed by STAR-ProBio, and inform STAR-ProBio of consumers' and businesses' awareness, behaviours and preferences related to sustainability of bio-based products.

- Three large Delphi surveys are scheduled for 2018; a 3-round survey of professionals in the bio-based sustainability field and a 2-round survey of consumers. The questionnaires of both rounds are being finalised and will be launched in May 2018, the second round is planned for the autumn of 2018 and the third round at the end of the year. Both surveys aim at 400 respondents by inviting several thousand people to participate in them.
- During the second year of STAR-ProBio, a Roundtable will be implemented for virtual discussions and exchange of views (via webinar and email exchange) with multiple external stakeholders. Discussions will be carried out focusing on the relevance of sustainability assessment factors and acceptance drivers will be implemented in. For example, the preliminary Delphi survey findings will be distributed and commented by roundtable. The Roundtable may also be invited by other WPs leaders to comment findings of their respective tasks.

10.3 Focus groups, symposia, forums and other events

Indicatively, participation in 21 events is planned for the second year of STAR-ProBio (Table 7).

Table 7: Indicative list of expected oral presentations and panel discussions in specialised events in the second year of STAR-ProBio

Nº	Event / Place	Date	Audience	WP in lead	Further details
1	Presentation at the International Conference on MATERIALS & ENERGY in San Sebastian, Spain	30/04/2018-04/05/2018	tbc	2	Title: Environmental sustainability assessment of biorefinery production chains from lignocellulosic biomass (Maria Teresa Moreira, Sara Bello, Carmen Ríos, Gumersindo Feijoo)
2	Oral presentation at SETAC Annual meeting in Rome, Italy	13/05/2018-17/05/2018	Sustainability specialists and non-technical audience	1 & 3	Title: Development of non-conventional LCA indicators for circular characteristics of bio-based products
3	Oral presentation at SETAC Annual meeting in Rome, Italy	13/05/2018-17/05/2018	Sustainability specialists and non-technical audience	2	Title: Process modelling and life cycle assessment of furandicarboxylic acid as a precursor of bioplastics.
4	Oral Presentation at SETAC 28th Annual Meeting in Rome, Italy	13/05/2018-17/05/2018	Sustainability specialists and non-technical audience	7	Title: Environmental, social and economic challenges towards a bio-based economy: the STAR-ProBio project, Sustainability Transition Assessment and Research of Bio-based Products
5	Poster Presentation at SETAC 28th Annual Meeting in Rome, Italy	13/05/2018-17/05/2018	Sustainability specialists and non-technical audience	6	Title: How the social pillar can be properly integrated into sustainability evaluation methodology? Evidence from bio-based products case study
6	Abstract accepted for an oral presentation at EUBCE in Copenhagen, Denmark	14/05/2018-18/05/2018	Researchers, industry and stakeholders of the BBE	1	Title: "Gaps and research demand analysis from current certification and standardisation in a

					sustainable biobased economy”
7	Presentation at conference BioBIGG “Business potentials for SMEs within the bioeconomy” in Gdańsk	24/05/2018	tbc	8,9	Title: Biorefinery processes in circular economy
8	Presentation at 6th International Conference on Sustainable Solid Waste Management (NAXOS) 2018 in Naxos, Greece	13/06/2018-16/06/2018	Business, stakeholders and scientific community in the areas of bio-based materials, bio-economy and sustainability analysis	4	Topic: The complexity of environmental indicators for the selection of lignocellulosic feedstocks in the production of biobased products.
9	Presentation at 6th International Conference on Sustainable Solid Waste Management (NAXOS) 2018 in Naxos, Greece	13/06/2018-16/06/2018	Business, stakeholders and scientific community in the areas of bio-based materials, bio-economy and sustainability analysis	4	Title: Inventory of alternative end-of-life routes of bio-based products – A Review (Briassoulis D, Pikasi A., Hiskakis M.)
10	Oral presentation at the Annual Congress on Plant Science and Bio Security ; 11-15 July 2018; Valencia, Spain	11/07/2018-15/07/2018	tbc	7, 8	Title: Land use efficiency indicators for bio-based production
11	Presentation at 6th Social Life Cycle Assessment conference in Pescara, Italy	10/09/2018-12/09/2018	tbc	6	Transitioning towards bioeconomy: assessing the social dimension through the lenses of the stakeholders
12	Poster or oral presentation at the 2nd International Conference on Bioresource Technology for Bioenergy, Bioproducts & Environmental Sustainability (BIORESTEC) in Sitges, Spain	16/09/2018-19/09/2018	tbc	4, 8, 9	To be decided
13	Course on Biorefinery: The Biorefinery as a multi-platform for Energy and Bioproducts	22/10/2018-23/10/2018	tbc	2	Fundamentals of Environmental assessment in biorefineries
14	Presentation at 4th Iberoamerican Congress On Biorefineries in Jaen, Spain	24/10/2018-26/10/2018	tbc	2	Environmental assessment of multiproduct biorefinery systems for the valorisation of

					chestnut shells
15	Presentation at 4th Iberoamerican Congress On Biorefineries in Jaen, Spain	24/10/2018-26/10/2018	tbc	2	Biotechnological production of apple pomace-based succinic acid – Environmental analysis
16	Presentation at 4th Iberoamerican Congress On Biorefineries in Jaen, Spain	24/10/2018-26/10/2018	tbc	2, 4	Title: 'Heterogeneous acid-catalysis for the production of furan-derived compounds from renewable carbohydrates: a life cycle approach' (Maria Teresa Moreira, Iana Cámara Salim, Sara Bello and Gumersindo Feijoo)
17	Presentation at 4th Iberoamerican Congress On Biorefineries in Jaen, Spain	24/10/2018-26/10/2018	tbc	2	'Process modelling and life cycle assessment of furandicarboxylic acid as a precursor of bioplastics' (Maria Teresa Moreira, Iana Cámara Salim, Pedro Méndez-Trelles, Sara Bello, Eva Rodil and Gumersindo Feijoo)
18	1 day Workshop at the University of York, UK	Q4 2018	Industry, researchers, academics and other interested stakeholders	3	Tracking Measuring and Reporting Responsible Innovation (an Environmental assessment workshop)
19	Internal cyclic seminar/ workshop at UWM, Poland	Q4 2018	Researchers	ALL	To be decided
20	Oral presentation at the VI Biogas Forum in Gdańsk, Poland	Q4 2018	tbc	8	Title: Anaerobic fermentation as an option of the end-of-life phase of bio-based products in the light of the European regulations
21	Public Engagement talk at SoapBox Science, UK	tbc	General public	3	Title: Circular products and choices: Science of material karma (UoY)

10.4 Second annual workshop

The second annual workshop is planned to take place as part of the 24th EURAS Annual Standardisation Conference "Standards for a Bio-Based Economy" between 13 and 15 June 2019 and will be hosted by the LUISS Guido Carli University of Rome.

The 24th EURAS Conference is co-organised by The European Academy for Standardisation (EURAS), Unitelma Sapienza – Bioeconomy in Transition Research Group (BiT-RG), STAR-ProBio (H2020 RIA programme - grant agreement no. 727740) and the Chair of Innovation Economics – Technische Universität Berlin.

The Project Management Committee of STAR-ProBio has concluded that co-organising the Second Annual Workshop together with the EURAS 2019 Conference is a very good opportunity for dissemination of results since the EURAS Conference will gather multiple stakeholders relevant for STAR-ProBio and papers of relevant topics for the STAR-ProBio debate will be presented during Conference. These topics include:

- Standardisation and Europe's research and innovation agenda
- Standards as a policy tool
- National or international policy and standardisation
- Standardisation of reference architectures and for systems engineering
- Standardisation of converging technologies
- Smart standardisation
- Standardisation roadmaps
- Standardisation and Open Source
- Standards and barriers to trade
- Standards and digitalization
- Standards as a driver for innovation
- Relation between standardisation and legislation
- Standardisation and quality infrastructure
- Legal aspects of standardisation
- Standards and knowledge transfer
- The impacts of standards and standardisation
- Quality of standards
- Role of industry and their associations in standardisation
- Standardisation via industry consortia
- History of standardisation
- Standardisation processes

Annex 1: Detailed forms for publications

Scientific publications

STAR-ProBio Scientific Publication Form #1

*Required

Name *: SARA GONZÁLEZ GARCÍA

E-mail Address *: sara.gonzalez@usc.es

Affiliation *: Universidade de Santiago de Compostela

Partner/s involved: Sara González-García; Beatriz Gullón

Have all partners involved and their organisations agreed on the proposed scientific publication? _x_Yes _No

Publication Title: Comparative environmental Life Cycle Assessment of integral revalorization of vine shoots from a biorefinery perspective

Author(s): Patricia Gullón, Beatriz Gullón, Izaskun Dávila, Jalel Labidi, Sara Gonzalez-Garcia

Date of publication (online) (dd/mm/yyyy): 15/12/2017

Date of publication (on paper) (dd/mm/yyyy): 15/12/2017

Status

In press

Published

Other:

Journal: Science of the Total Environment

Volume (issue): 624

Pages: 225-240

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.12.036>

URL:

Access

Restricted

Open

WP relevance

WP 1

WP 2

WP 3

WP 4

WP 5

WP 6

WP 7

- WP 8
- WP 9
- All

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see *Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy*) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included?

Yes No

STAR-ProBio Scientific Publication Form # 2

*Required

Name *: Pasquale Marcello Falcone

E-mail Address *: pasquale.falcone@unitelmasapienza.it

Affiliation *: Unitelma Sapienza

Partner/s involved: Unitelma

Have all partners involved and their organisations agreed on the proposed scientific publication? Yes

Publication Title: Social Life Cycle Approach as a Tool for Promoting the Market Uptake of Bio-Based Products from a Consumer Perspective

Author(s): Pasquale Marcello Falcone and Enrica Imbert

Date of publication (online): (30/03/2018)

Date of publication (on paper)

Status

Published

Journal: Sustainability

Volume (issue): 10 (4)

Pages: 1- 22

DOI: [10.3390/su10041031](https://doi.org/10.3390/su10041031)

URL: <http://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/10/4/1031>

Access

Open

WP relevance

WP 6

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included?

Yes

STAR-ProBio Scientific Publication Form # 3

*Required

Name *: Pasquale Marcello Falcone

E-mail Address *: pasquale.falcone@unitelma.it

Affiliation *: Unitelma Sapienza – University of Rome

Partner/s involved:

Have all partners involved and their organisations agreed on the proposed scientific publication? No other partner involved

Publication Title: Recenti sviluppi della bioeconomia in Italia: un driver di sviluppo per il Mezzogiorno? (italian)

Author(s): P.M. Falcone, S. Fumagalli, E. Imbert, C. Imbriani, P. Morone, S. Trenti

Date of publication (on paper) (07/11/2017):

Status: Published

Book: Rapporto Svimez 2017 sull'economia del Mezzogiorno

Publisher: Società Editrice il Mulino

Pages: 547 - 565

ISBN: 978-88-15-27354-3

URL: <https://www.mulino.it/isbn/9788815273543>

Access: Restricted

WP relevance: WP 1

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included?

No

Non-scientific publications

STAR-ProBio General Dissemination Form # 1

*Required information

Name * Janusz Gołaszewski

E-mail Address * janusz.golaszewski@uwm.edu.pl

Affiliation * University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn

Type of activity:

- Publication in newspaper
- Publication in magazine**
- Web publication
- TV broadcast
- Radio broadcast
- Press release
- Policy brief
- Teaching
- PhD thesis
- Master thesis
- Website article
- Other:

Partner(s) involved:

Have all partners involved and their organisations agreed on the proposed activity? XYes ___No

Title of dissemination activity: Article in polish: "Dzisiaj odpad-jutro surowiec"

Date (dd/mm/yyyy): August-September/2017

Place (country/city): Poland/Olsztyn

Type of audience (e.g. scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students, conservationists, ecologists, general public, etc.): **researchers, students, general public**

Size of audience (estimated no.): **circulation about 2.200**

Geographical coverage (World, Europe, etc.): **local**

Countries addressed: Poland

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included?

Yes No (That was a short information of SPB, adnotation of STAR-ProBio was given in the text)

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL...):

http://www.uwm.edu.pl/sites/default/files/wiad-uniwer/2017/wu-2017-08_09.pdf

General Dissemination Form # 2

*Required information

Name *Mathilde Crepy, Honey Kohan

E-mail Address *mathilde.crepy@ecostandard.org, honey.kohan@ecostandard.org

Affiliation * ECOS

Type of activity:

- Publication in newspaper
- Publication in magazine
- Web publication
- TV broadcast
- Radio broadcast
- Press release
- Policy brief
- Teaching
- PhD thesis
- Master thesis
- Website article YES
- Other:

Partner(s) involved:

Have all partners involved and their organisations agreed on the proposed activity? No

Title of dissemination activity:

Date (dd/mm/yyyy): 31/10/2017

Place (country/city): ECOS' website: <http://ecostandard.org/>

Type of audience (e.g. scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students, conservationists, ecologists, general public, etc.): general public, ECOS' website readers

Size of audience (estimated no.): 1000+ a month

Geographical coverage (World, Europe, etc.): N/A

Countries addressed: N/A

Are EU acknowledgement and STAR-ProBio logo properly included in the presentations? N/A (no presentation). Article redirects audience to project website.

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL...):

Text of web article

STAR-ProBio – General Assembly

With their broad range of applications – from construction to tyres ; from cosmetics to toys – bio-based products (products made from biological resources) continue to receive a lot of political attention. Bio-based products can help improve the environmental profile of products since they can replace synthetic materials such as chemicals or plastics. However, their use needs to be balanced so as not to strip nature of biodiversity, and to not drive the clearing of land or the change from food crops to grow crops for industrial use.

ECOS is a partner in a Horizon 2020 project aiming to encourage the production and use of sustainable bio-based products by identifying key criteria characterising these products and enabling comparison with their fossil based counterparts. The project was kicked off in May 2017 and runs until April 2020. In mid-October ECOS attended the project's first general assembly meeting which offered a very good opportunity to build a common understanding of the issues at stake and objectives of the project between the 15 partners.

The goal of the project is to develop a comprehensive sustainability scheme applying to bio-based products, including standards, labels and certifications. The resulting toolbox will build on existing standards including existing Life Cycle Assessment standards such as ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 and existing sustainability certification systems.

During the first 6 months of the project, ECOS and the other project partners have been carrying out comparative analyses of existing sustainability standards and certification schemes applying to bio-based products. The objective at this stage is to better understand what is already covered by standards and certification systems, how, and whether they can be the basis for sustainability or environmental claims.

For more information, please visit the STAR-Pro-Bio [website](#).

STAR-ProBio General Dissemination Form # 3

*Required information

Name (in alphabetic order): Luana Ladu and Simone Wurster

E-mail Address: luana.ladu@tu-berlin.de and simone.wurster@tu-berlin.de

Affiliation: TU Berlin, Innovation Economics

Type of activity:

- Publication in newspaper
- Publication in magazine
- Web publication
- TV broadcast
- Radio broadcast
- Press release
- Policy brief
- Teaching
- PhD thesis
- Master thesis
- Website article
- Other:

Partner(s) involved: TU Berlin

Have all partners involved and their organisations agreed on the proposed activity? Yes No

Title of dissemination activity: Erste Ergebnisse aus dem Europäischen Forschungsprojekt STAR-ProBio

Date (dd/mm/yyyy): January 2018 issue

Place (country/city): DIN Mitteilungen + elektronorm. Zeitschrift für Deutsche, Europäische und Internationale Normung, January 2018, p. 3

Type of audience (e.g. scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students, conservationists, ecologists, general public, etc.): businesses, public procurers, users, certification bodies, researchers, policy makers etc.

Size of audience (estimated no.): 4,000

Geographical coverage (World, Europe, etc.): Germany

Countries addressed: Germany

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included?

x Yes ___No

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL...): regarding the previous question: The short text (the number of characters was limited) mentions that STAR-ProBio is an EU project and includes information on STAR-ProBio's website

STAR-ProBio General Dissemination Form # 4

*Required information

Name * Louise Summerton

E-mail Address * louise.summerton@york.ac.uk

Affiliation * University of York

Type of activity:

- Publication in newspaper
- Publication in magazine
- Web publication
- TV broadcast
- Radio broadcast
- Press release
- Policy brief
- Teaching
- PhD thesis
- Master thesis
- Website article
- Other:

Partner(s) involved: SQ Consult and Unitelma

Have all partners involved and their organisations agreed on the proposed activity? Yes No

Title of dissemination activity: STAR-ProBio BBI-JU SEED through the BioWatch dissemination tool of the BIOWAYS project

Date (dd/mm/yyyy): 09/02/2018

Place (country/city): N/A

Type of audience (e.g. scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students, conservationists, ecologists, general public, etc.): industry, scientists, researchers and political stakeholders

Size of audience (estimated no.):

Geographical coverage (World, Europe, etc.):

Countries addressed:

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included?

_x_Yes _No

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL...):

BIOWATCH is an online, interactive platform that provides projects in the bioeconomy sector with a free service to position themselves alongside one another and communicate their results directly to industry, political stakeholders, the media and the general public in an engaging and accessible format.

The overall aim of BIOWATCH is to raise awareness of bio-based projects and bio-products, and also promote further collaboration between research bodies, organisations and universities.

In this online research library, projects are presented in the form of multi-media digital brochures, named SEEDs. <http://library.bioways.eu/SEEDHTML/player.php>

STAR-ProBio General Dissemination Form # 5

*Required information

Name * Briassoulis Demetres

E-mail Address * briassou@aua.gr

Affiliation * Professor

Type of activity:

- Publication in newspaper
- Publication in magazine
- Web publication
- TV broadcast
- Radio broadcast
- Press release
- Policy brief
- Teaching
- PhD thesis
- Master thesis
- Website article
- Other:

Partner(s) involved: SQ Consult and Unitelma

Have all partners involved and their organisations agreed on the proposed activity? Yes No

Title of dissemination activity:

Date (dd/mm/yyyy): 2/3/2018

Place (country/city): Greece/Athens

Type of audience (e.g. scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students, conservationists, ecologists, general public, etc.):

Scientists, researchers, students, general public, etc

Size of audience (estimated no.): **65000 per month**

Geographical coverage (World, Europe, etc.): **Greece**

Countries addressed: Greece

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included?

_x_Yes _No

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL...):

<https://www2.aua.gr/el/news-events/nea/axiologisi-kai-ereyna-metavasis-stin-aeiforia-ton-viogenon-proionton>

STAR-ProBio General Dissemination Form # 6

*Required information

Name: Xavier Bengoa

E-mail Address: xavier.bengoa@quantis-intl.com

Affiliation: Quantis

Type of activity:

Web publication

Partner(s) involved: SQ Consult and Unitelma

Have all partners involved and their organisations agreed on the proposed activity? No

Title of dissemination activity: *Beyond LCA: Why Impact Evaluation Strengthens the Business Case for Bio-based Plastics*

Date (dd/mm/yyyy): 03/04/2018

Place (country/city): Lausanne, Switzerland

Type of audience (e.g. scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students, conservationists, ecologists, general public, etc.):

Size of audience (estimated no.): 500

Geographical coverage (World, Europe, etc.): World

Countries addressed: France, UK, Belgium, Germany, Netherlands, Denmark, Sweden, Austria, Italy, Spain, Switzerland, Greece, USA, Canada, Colombia, Brazil, Chile, New Zealand, Australia

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included?

No (not applicable, only a link to STAR-ProBio website is provided)

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL...): This is a general position article on bio-based plastics, with reference to STAR-ProBio. URL: <https://quantis-intl.com/bio-based-plastics/>

STAR-ProBio General Dissemination Form # 7

*Required information

Name (in alphabetic order): Luana Ladu, Stefan Mayer and Simone Wurster

E-mail Address: luana.ladu@tu-berlin.de, Stefan.mayer@dbfz.de
simone.wurster@tu-berlin.de

Affiliation: TU Berlin, Innovation Economics

Type of activity:

Publication in newspaper

Publication in magazine

Web publication

TV broadcast

Radio broadcast

Press release

Policy brief

Teaching

PhD thesis

Master thesis

Website article

Other:

Partner(s) involved: TU Berlin

Have all partners involved and their organisations agreed on the proposed activity? Yes No

Title of dissemination activity: Förderung biobasierter Produkte durch Normung und Zertifizierung

Date (dd/mm/yyyy): April 2018 issue

Place (country/city): DIN Mitteilungen + elektronorm. Zeitschrift für Deutsche, Europäische und Internationale Normung, DIN Mitteilungen April 2018, 13-21

Type of audience (e.g. scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students, conservationists, ecologists, general public, etc.): businesses, public procurers, users, certification bodies, researchers, policy makers etc.

Size of audience (estimated no.): 4,000

Geographical coverage (World, Europe, etc.): Germany

Countries addressed: Germany

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included?

x Yes ___No

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL...): regarding the previous question:
The short text (the number of characters was limited) mentions that STAR-ProBio is an EU project and includes information on STAR-ProBio's website

Annex 2: Detailed forms for focus groups, symposia, forums and other events

Internal workshops and experts focus groups

STAR-ProBio Symposia and meetings form # 1

*Required information

Name *Centre for Bioeconomy and Renewable Energies (CBE0)

E-mail Address *cbeo@uwm.edu.pl

Affiliation *University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn

Presentation at scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other:

Organisation of scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop: 1st Internal Workshop "Principles, criteria and indicators for sustainability transition assessment to circular and bio-based economy"

Other:

Other type of activity

Organisation of training course

Direct interactions with stakeholders

Other:

Partner(s) involved: UWM (University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn)

Title of event: "Principles, criteria and indicators for sustainability transition assessment to circular and bio-based economy"

Type of presentation (talk, poster, abstract, PR materials distributed...): talk

Title of presentation: WP1, 2,3, 4,7,8,9,10- summary of current research of SPB work packages realized by UWM

Authors of presentation:

1. Janusz Gołaszewski

2. Jakub Zięty

3. Michał Krzyżaniak

4. Irena Wojnowska-Baryła

5. Mariusz Stolarski

6. Krystyna Żuk-Gołaszewska

7. Ewelina Olba-Zięty

Have all authors and their organisations agreed on the proposed presentation?

XYes ___No

Date (dd/mm/yyyy): **15/09/2017**

Place (country/city): **Poland/Olsztyn**

Type of audience (scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students, conservationists, ecologists, general public, etc.): **researchers**

Size of audience (estimated no.): **15**

Geographical coverage (World, Europe, etc.): local

Countries: **Poland**

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included in the presentations? X Yes ___No

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL, etc.):

STAR-ProBio Symposia and meetings form # 2

*Required information

Name: Stefan Majer and David Moosmann (DBFZ), Simone Wurster (TUB)

E-mail Address: Stefan.Majer@dbfz.de

Affiliation: DBFZ

Presentation at scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other:

Organisation of scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other:

Other type of activity

Organisation of training course

Direct interactions with stakeholders

Other:

Partner(s) involved: DBFZ, TUB, SQ Consult

Title of event: WP1 Conference - Focus group

Type of presentation (talk, poster, abstract, PR materials distributed...): **Web conference (focus group)**

Title of presentation: "Gap analyses of existing sustainability schemes and technical standards, web-conference organised by WP1"

Authors of presentation:

1. Stefan Majer (DBFZ)

2. David Moosmann (DBFZ)

3. Simone Wurster (TUB)

Have all authors and their organisations agreed on the proposed presentation?

X Yes ___No

Date (dd/mm/yyyy): **26/10/2017**

Place (country/city): **Streamlined from Berlin, Germany**

Type of audience (scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students, conservationists, ecologists, general public, etc.): **researchers**

Size of audience (estimated no.): **19**

Geographical coverage (World, Europe, etc.): Europe

Countries: EU

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included in the presentations? X Yes ___No

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL, etc.): **The experts discussion aimed at analysing identified gaps and analysing possible synergies among schemes and standards**

STAR-ProBio General Dissemination Form # 3

*Required information

Name (in alphabetic order): Luana Ladu and Simone Wurster

E-mail Address: luana.ladu@tu-berlin.de and simone.wurster@tu-berlin.de

Affiliation: TU Berlin, Innovation Economics

Type of activity:

- Publication in newspaper
- Publication in magazine
- Web publication
- TV broadcast
- Radio broadcast
- Press release
- Policy brief
- Teaching
- PhD thesis
- Master thesis
- Website article
- Other: Focus Group event

Partner(s) involved: TU Berlin, Unitelma, SQ Consult, ECOS

Have all partners involved and their organisations agreed on the proposed activity? x Yes No

Title of dissemination activity: Sustainability Assessment Factors for Bio-Based Products

Date (dd/mm/yyyy): January 29, 2018

Place (country/city): web-based workshop

Type of audience (e.g. scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students, conservationists, ecologists, general public, etc.): public procurers, businesses and business associations, standardisation and certification professionals, research, NGOs

Size of audience (estimated no.): approx. 20 + a few interested parties who could not participate but asked STAR-ProBio for the results

Geographical coverage (World, Europe, etc.): Europe

Countries addressed: for example EU in general: Belgium, Germany, Italy, Spain and The Netherlands + various additional dissemination activities by parties who collaborate with STAR-ProBio, see e.g.:

<http://www.bioways.eu/download.php?f=168&l=en&key=72e5f392eb03b10a803b564e9d4f3eff>

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included?

x Yes ___No

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL...):

STAR-ProBio Symposia and meetings form # 4

*Required information

Name * Centre for Bioeconomy and Renewable Energies, University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn

E-mail Address * cbeo@uwm.edu.pl

Affiliation * University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn

Presentation at scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other:

Organisation of scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop: **Internal workshop/seminar at UWM to summary activity our team in the frame of the STAR-ProBio**

Title of seminar: *Sustainability Transition Assessment and Research of Bio-based Products: Progression and Shortcomings of Current Sustainability Standards of Bio-based Products*

Other:

Other type of activity

Organisation of training course

Direct interactions with stakeholders

Other:

Partner(s) involved: UWM team of SPB

Title of event: *Sustainability Transition Assessment and Research of Bio-based Products: Progression and Shortcomings of Current Sustainability Standards of Bio-based Products (Internal Seminar at UWM)*

Type of presentation- talk

Title of presentation:

WP1- a summary of WP1;

WP2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 10 -summary of current research of SPB work packages realized by UWM;

Authors of presentation:

- 1. Janusz Gołaszewski**
- 2. Ewelina Olba-Zięty**
- 3. Monika Nitkiewicz**
- 4. Anna Karwowska**
- 5. Mirosława Witkowska-Dąbrowska**
- 6. Jakub Zięty**
- 7. Andrzej Juszcuk**
- 8. Michał Łuczyński**
- 9. Krystyna Żuk-Gołaszewska**
- 10. Michał Krzykowski**
- 11. Katarzyna Bernat**
- 12. Dorota Kulikowska**
- 13. Barbara Kalisz**
- 14. Mariusz Stolarski**
- 15. Wioleta Radawiec**
- 16. Michał Krzyżaniak**
- 17. Urszula Szymańska**

Have all authors and their organisations agreed on the proposed presentation?

X Yes ___No

Date (dd/mm/yyyy): 22.03.2018

Place (country/city): Poland/Olsztyn

Type of audience: researchers

Size of audience (estimated no.): 20

Geographical coverage (World, Europe, etc.): local

Countries: Poland

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included in the presentations? XYes ___No

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL, etc.):

Oral presentations and panel discussions

STAR-ProBio Symposia and meetings form # 1

*Required information

Name * Francesca Govoni

E-mail Address * francesca.govoni@unitelma.it

Affiliation * Unitelma

Presentation at scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other

Organisation of scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other:

Other type of activity

Organisation of training course

Direct interactions with stakeholders

Other: Coordinators Day

Partner(s) involved: Unitelma and TUB

Title of event: Coordinators Day

Type of presentation: PowerPoint presentation

Title of presentation: Luana Ladu (TUB) and Francesca Govoni (Unitelma) presented STAR-ProBio to officers of the European Commission as well as coordinators of other similar projects. This was also a great opportunity to liaise with other projects with overlapping interests.

Authors of presentation: Luana Ladu (TUB)

Have all authors and their organisations agreed on the proposed presentation?

Yes

Date: 22/06/2017

Place: Brussels

Type of audience: Coordinators of European projects and Officers of the European Commission

Size of audience (estimated no.): More than 100 participants

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see *Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy*) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included in the presentations? Yes

STAR-ProBio Symposia and meetings form # 2

*Required information

Name *Diego Marazza

E-mail Address *diego.marazza@unibo.it

Affiliation *University of Bologna

Presentation at scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other:

Organisation of scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other:

Other type of activity

Organisation of training course

Direct interactions with stakeholders

Other:

Partner(s) involved:

Title of event: 50th Int. Seminars on Planetary Emergencies Erice, 21 August 2017 - My short talk was given with the title

Type of presentation (talk, poster, abstract, PR materials distributed...): **talk**

Title of presentation: "The Bio-Economy and the transition towards circular Economy - Sustainability schemes, standards, labels and certification of biobased products "

Authors of presentation: **Diego Marazza**

Have all authors and their organisations agreed on the proposed presentation?

Yes No

Date (dd/mm/yyyy): **21 August 2017**

Place (country/city): Erice

Type of audience (scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students, conservationists, ecologists, general public, etc.):

scientists, researchers, policy makers,

Size of audience (estimated no.): 100

Geographical coverage (World, Europe, etc.): World

Countries: USA, UK, Germany, Switzerland, South Korea, Japan, Vietnam, Turkey, India, Italy, Zimbabwe, Senegal

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included in the presentations? __Yes __X_No

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL, etc.):

This talk was intended primarily as a presentation of my personal activity and I caught the opportunity to link it to STAR-ProBio project.

As a direct consequence I invited Prof. Carmine di Figlio in the Advisory Board

STAR-ProBio Symposia and meetings form # 3

*Required information

Name *Janusz Gołaszewski

E-mail Address * janusz.golaszewski@uwm.edu.pl

Affiliation * University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn

Presentation at scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other:

Organisation of scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other:

Other type of activity

Organisation of training course

Direct interactions with stakeholders

Other:

Partner(s) involved:

Title of event: Workshop BioBIGG "State of play of bio-economy in the South Baltic Area"

Type of presentation (talk, poster, abstract, PR materials distributed...): **talk**

Title of presentation: "Biorefinery processes in circular economy"

Authors of presentation: Janusz Gołaszewski

Have all authors and their organisations agreed on the proposed presentation?

xYes No

Date (dd/mm/yyyy): **6/12/2017**

Place (country/city): **Poland/Gdańsk**

Type of audience (scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students, conservationists, ecologists, general public, etc.): **scientists, researchers, students, ecologists**

Size of audience (estimated no.): **40**

Geographical coverage (World, Europe, etc.): **Europe**

Countries: **Sweden, Denmark, Germany, Poland**

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included in the presentations? Yes No

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL, etc.):

STAR-ProBio Symposia and meetings form # 4

*Required information

Name : Kadambari Lokesh

E-mail Address : kadambari.lokesh@york.ac.uk

Affiliation : Green Chemistry Post-Doctoral Research Associate

Presentation at scientific symposia

- Conference
- Meeting
- Workshop
- Other:

Organisation of scientific symposia

- Conference
- Meeting
- Workshop
- Other:

Other type of activity

- Organisation of training course
- Direct interactions with stakeholders
- Other:

Partner(s) involved: Luana Ladu

Title of event: ECO-BIO Challenges in Building a Sustainable Biobased Economy

Type of presentation : Oral presentation

Title of presentation: Bridging the gaps for a 'circular' bio-economy: selection criteria, bio-based value chain and stakeholder mapping

Authors of presentation: Kadambari Lokesh, Luana Ladu, Louise Summerton

Have all authors and their organisations agreed on the proposed presentation?

X Yes ___No

Date 07/03/2018

Place : Dublin, Ireland

Type of audience: scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students, conservationists, ecologists

Size of audience : 250 delegates

Geographical coverage: World

Countries: All but the US, South America and Europe had more representatives

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included in the presentations? X Yes ___No

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL, etc.):

<https://www.elsevier.com/events/conferences/eco-bio>

STAR-ProBio Symposia and meetings form # 5

*Required information

Name * Luana Ladu

E-mail Address * luana.ladu@tu-berlin.de

Affiliation * TU Berlin

Presentation at scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other:

Organisation of scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other:

Other type of activity

Organisation of training course

Direct interactions with stakeholders

Other:

Partner(s) involved: TUB

Title of event: ECO BIO 2018

Type of presentation (talk, poster, abstract, PR materials distributed...): talk

Title of presentation: Forecasting innovations and technological trends in the european bio-based industry: Experts view and patent analysis

Authors of presentation: Luana Ladu

Have all authors and their organisations agreed on the proposed presentation? Yes No

Date (6/03(2018):

Place (Irland/Dublin):

Type of audience (scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students, conservationists, ecologists, general public, etc.): Scientist, Researchers, Students, industry, NGOs.

Size of audience (estimated no.): estimated 500 participants

Geographical coverage (World, Europe, etc.): World, however mostly from Europe and Brazil

Countries:

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included in the presentations? __Yes __No

NO. This presentation was given in the framework of the STAR4BBI project (also covering the costs). However, there STAR-ProBio project was mentioned during the presentation.

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL, etc.):

STAR-ProBio Symposia and meetings form # 6

*Required information

Name * Valentina Elena Tartiu

E-mail Address * valentina.tartiu@unitelma.it

Affiliation * Unitelma

Presentation at scientific symposia

X Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other:

Organisation of scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other:

Other type of activity

Organisation of training course

Direct interactions with stakeholders

Other:

Partner(s) involved: Unitelma

Title of event: 3rd edition of the NEST-conference, "New Frontiers in Sustainability Transitions"

Type of presentation (talk, poster, abstract, PR materials distributed...): talk

Title of presentation: How can we shape circular bioeconomy in a Multi-Level Perspective?

Authors of presentation: Valentina Elena Tartiu, Almona Tani and Piergiuseppe Morone

Have all authors and their organisations agreed on the proposed presentation?

Yes

Date (dd/mm/yyyy): 15-16/03/2018

Place (country/city): Utrecht, The Netherlands

Type of audience (scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students, conservationists, ecologists, general public, etc.): PhD students and ECRs, senior researchers

Size of audience (estimated no.): --

Geographical coverage (World, Europe, etc.): Europe

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included in the presentations? Yes

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL, etc.): --

STAR-ProBio Symposia and meetings form # 7

*Required information

Name * Mathilde Crepy

E-mail Address * Mathilde.crepy@ecostandard.org

Affiliation * ECOS

Presentation at scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop: presentation of STAR-ProBio project focussing on communications aspects

Other:

Organisation of scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other:

Other type of activity

Organisation of training course

Direct interactions with stakeholders

Other: Mutual learning workshop: Maximizing collaboration among EC funded projects communicating about Bioeconomy (Organised by the Biovoices consortium, with the support of the European Commission (DG RTD))

Partner(s) involved: All, mostly relevant for WP 10

Title of event: Mutual learning workshop: Maximizing collaboration among EC funded projects communicating about Bioeconomy

Type of presentation (talk, poster, abstract, PR materials distributed...): **Powerpoint presentation**

Title of presentation: **Presentation of STAR ProBio**

Authors of presentation: **Mathilde Crepy**

Have all authors and their organisations agreed on the proposed presentation?
No

Date (dd/mm/yyyy): 28/3/2018

Place (country/city): Brussels

Type of audience (scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students, conservationists, ecologists, general public, etc.): policy makers and other H2020 project representatives

Size of audience (estimated no.): 23 H-2020 projects representatives + 5 European Commission's representative (around 30 participants)

Geographical coverage (World, Europe, etc.): EU

Countries:

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included in the presentations? Yes – use of the ppt template

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL, etc.): minutes and follow-up actions available here:
<https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1wVcrPkcm6LuiWYnC6gTpNJdBWkUtLjE1>

STAR-ProBio Symposia and meetings form # 8

*Required information

Name * Mathilde Crépy & Doreen Fedrigo-Fazio (ECOS); Sergio Ugarte (SQ Consult)

E-mail Address * mathilde.crepy@ecostandard.org & doreen.fedrigo@ecostandard.org s.ugarte@sqconsult.com

Affiliation * ECOS and SQ Consult

Presentation at scientific symposia

___ Conference: Final event of the European innovation and research project ButaNext. The event is entitled '**Innovation in the bioeconomy: overcoming barriers for sustainable bio-based products & biofuels**'.

ECOS (as STAR-ProBio partner) will join the 1-hour panel discussion on market barriers. The contribution of ECOS in this panel will focus on standards.

Next to the panel discussion, a poster session will take place at the event. STAR-ProBio is invited to participate to this session too.

___ Meeting

___ Workshop

___ Other:

Organisation of scientific symposia

___ Conference

___ Meeting

___ Workshop

___ Other:

Other type of activity

___ Organisation of training course

___ Direct interactions with stakeholders

___ Other:

Partner(s) involved: Panel discussion: ECOS ; poster (partner TBC). This activity is mostly relevant for WP 5, and hence to be agreed upon by WP leader TU Berlin.

Title of event: Innovation in the bioeconomy: overcoming barriers for sustainable bio-based products & biofuels

Type of presentation (talk, poster, abstract, PR materials distributed...): panel discussion, poster (tbc)

Title of presentation: The contribution of sustainability standards to bioeconomy (tbc)

Authors of presentation: Mathilde Crêpy & Doreen Fedrigo

Have all authors and their organisations agreed on the proposed presentation?
Yes No

Date (dd/mm/yyyy): 12/04/2018

Place (country/city): Brussels

Type of audience (scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students, conservationists, ecologists, general public, etc.): scientists, researchers, industries, NGOs & policy makers

Size of audience (estimated no.): around 80 people

Geographical coverage (World, Europe, etc.): Europe

Countries: EU countries

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included in the presentations? Yes No

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL, etc.):

STAR-ProBio Symposia and meetings form # 9

*Required information

Name * Piergiuseppe Morone

E-mail Address * piergiuseppe.morone@unitelmasapienza.it

Affiliation * Unitelma

Presentation at scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other:

Organisation of scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other:

Other type of activity

Organisation of training course

Direct interactions with stakeholders

Other:

Partner(s) involved: Unitelma, TUB

Title of event: International Workshop – Measuring the Sustainability of the Bioeconomy: Where do we stand/What gaps/What next?

Type of presentation (talk, poster, abstract, PR materials distributed...): Panelist

Title of presentation: Panellists

Authors of presentation: Piergiuseppe Morone, Luana Ladu

Have all authors and their organisations agreed on the proposed presentation?

Yes

Date (dd/mm/yyyy): 17-18/04/2018

Place (country/city): Berlin

Type of audience (scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students, conservationists, ecologists, general public, etc.): Scientists, researchers, policy makers,

Size of audience (estimated no.): --42 researchers

Geographical coverage (World, Europe, etc.): World

Countries: --

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included in the presentations? Yes

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL, etc.): --

Piergiuseppe Morone (UNITELMA) and Luana Ladu (TUB) participated in the central panel discussion of the workshop and presented the projects and the gap analysis conducted in WP1

STAR-ProBio Symposia and meetings form # 10

*Required information

Name * Sergio Ugarte
E-mail Address * s.ugarte@sqconsult.com
Affiliation * SQ Consult

Presentation at scientific symposia

- Conference
 Meeting
 Workshop
 Other:

Organisation of scientific symposia

- Conference
 Meeting
 Workshop
 Other:

Other type of activity

- Organisation of training course
 Direct interactions with stakeholders
 Other:

Partner(s) involved: SQ Consult, DBFZ and TUB

Title of event: "Governing sustainability of bioenergy, biomaterial and bioproduct supply chains from forest and agricultural landscapes"

Type of presentation (talk, poster, abstract, PR materials distributed...): Talk at IEA task 43 Conference

Title of presentation: "Gaps in sustainability tools and schemes for bio-based products and stakeholders preferences and expectations"

Authors of presentation: Sergio Ugarte (SQ Consult), Stefan Majer, David Moosmann (DBFZ), Luana Ladu, Simone Wurster (TUB),

Have all authors and their organisations agreed on the proposed presentation?
 Yes No

Date (dd/mm/yyyy): 17-19 April 2018

Place (country/city): Copenhagen, Denmark

Type of audience (scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students, conservationists, ecologists, general public, etc.): Researchers, producers of biomass for bioenergy, bio-chemicals and biomaterials, and other stakeholders from the forest, agriculture, biogas and bioenergy sectors

Size of audience (estimated no.): 100 people

Geographical coverage (World, Europe, etc.): World

Countries: Focus EU

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included in the presentations? Yes No

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL, etc.):

URL: <http://ign.ku.dk/bioenergy-conf-2018/>

Abstract:

Bio-based products represent a great opportunity to reconcile sustainable long-term growth through the prudent and responsible use of renewable resources for agriculture and industry. Two problems are identified to promote their market uptake of such bio-based products: Lack of tools to assess their sustainability and consumer acceptance. The development and use of sustainability assessment schemes for bio-based products contributes to an evidence-based view of the economic, social and environmental impact/benefits of bio-based solutions. However, the scope of present-day schemes and tools focus on biomass and bioenergy and are limited to the sustainable production and processing of biomass, up to the distribution of end-products. The use phase or end-of-life is in most cases not covered. Regarding consumers' acceptance, bio-based products are partially immune to criticisms on use of land, water and other resources that biomass fuel suffers. However, consumers are not fully ready to replace a wide range of traditional products (plastics, cosmetics, fragrance chemicals, etc.) with bio-based substitutes mainly because of the perceived lower performance and higher costs. In particular for bio-based products originating from waste, acceptance must be progressively built up. The Horizon 2020 funded project STAR-ProBio (2017-2020) supports the development of a horizontally applicable blueprint for improving existing or creating new sustainability schemes. The proposed horizontal approach will provide access to sustainability schemes to a broader set of bio-based products including: fibres, cellulose-derived chemicals, composites, plastics and microbeads, biolubricants and hydraulic fluids. This will impact the construction, automotive and health care markets. Research in STAR-ProBio involves desk-work, stakeholders' analysis, qualitative and quantitative assessments, surveys, case studies and alternative scenarios comparison. Intermediate results of two work-packages are presented and discussed in this paper. Identified gaps & missing indicators in existing sustainability tools & schemes are analysed in terms of their relevance for the sustainability of bio-based solutions. The preferences and expectations that consumers, producers and public procurers have for the assessment of the sustainability of bio-products are analysed in terms their importance and efficiency for the priorities of the different stakeholders in the value chain. A discussion of how those gaps and stakeholders preferences are related follows to inform the opportunities and challenges that sustainability tools and schemes serving bio-based products face. Finally, a first reflection of how STAR-ProBio envisions the discussion for the integration of tools in European regulation will be presented.

Attendance to specialised seminars

STAR-ProBio Symposia and meetings form # 1

*Required information

Name * Francesca Govoni

E-mail Address * francesca.govoni@unitelma.it

Affiliation * Unitelma

Presentation at scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other

Organisation of scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other: Seminar

Other type of activity

Organisation of training course

Direct interactions with stakeholders

Other

Partner(s) involved: Unitelma

Title of event: Seminar "Life Cycle Assessment and waste management: theory and practice"

Type of presentation: PowerPoint presentation

Title of presentation: Seminar "Life Cycle Assessment and waste management: theory

and practice"

Authors of presentation: Carlo Ingraio

Have all authors and their organisations agreed on the proposed presentation?

Yes

Date: 27/09/2017

Place: Rome, Italy

Type of audience: STAR-ProBio team

Size of audience: 5 people

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and

Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included in the presentations? Yes

STAR-ProBio Symposia and meetings form # 2

*Required information

Name * : Luana Ladu

E-mail Address *: luana.ladu(at)tu-berlin.de

Affiliation *: TU Berlin

Presentation at scientific symposia

- Conference (no presentation, just attendance for networking)
 Meeting
 Workshop
 Other:

Organisation of scientific symposia

- Conference
 Meeting
 Workshop
 Other:

Other type of activity

- Organisation of training course
 Direct interactions with stakeholders
 Other:

Partner(s) involved: TUB

Title of event: 12th European Bioplastics Conference 2017 in Berlin

Type of presentation (talk, poster, abstract, PR materials distributed...):

Title of presentation: no presentation

Authors of presentation:

Have all authors and their organisations agreed on the proposed presentation?

Yes No

Date: 28-29/11(2017):

Place (Germany/Berlin):

Type of audience (scientists, researchers, directors, editors, policy makers, students, conservationists, ecologists, general public, etc.):

Size of audience (estimated no.):

Geographical coverage (World, **Europe**, etc.):

Countries:

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included in the presentations? __Yes __No

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL, etc.):

STAR-ProBio Symposia and meetings form # 3

*Required information

Name * Francesca Govoni

E-mail Address * francesca.govoni@unitelma.it

Affiliation * Unitelma

Presentation at scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other

Organisation of scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other: Seminar

Other type of activity

Organisation of training course

Direct interactions with stakeholders

Other

Partner(s) involved: Unitelma

Title of event: Seminar "Empirical Research Avenues for Regional Policy Elaboration"

Type of presentation: PowerPoint presentation

Title of presentation: Seminar "Empirical Research Avenues for Regional Policy Elaboration"

Authors of presentation: Marco Capasso

Have all authors and their organisations agreed on the proposed presentation?

Yes

Date: 04/12/2017

Place: Rome, Italy

Type of audience: STAR-ProBio team

Size of audience: 6 people

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included in the presentations? Yes

Annex 3: Detailed forms for other general dissemination activities

STAR-ProBio General Dissemination Form # 1

*Required information

Name : Kadambari Lokesh

E-mail Address : kadambari.lokesh@york.ac.uk

Affiliation: Green Chemistry Post- Doctoral Research Associate

Type of activity:

- Publication in newspaper
- Publication in magazine
- Web publication
- TV broadcast
- Radio broadcast
- Press release
- Policy brief
- Teaching
- PhD thesis
- Master thesis
- Website article
- Other: Podcast by SuperWomeninScience

Partner(s) involved: None

Have all partners involved and their organisations agreed on the proposed activity? X Yes ___No

Title of dissemination activity: Science behind your Product Choices

Date 16/01/2018

Place : York, UK

Type of audience: scientists, researchers, students, conservationists, general public

Size of audience (estimated no.): 276 play-counts

Geographical coverage : Worldwide

Countries addressed: N/A

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included?

X Yes ___No

Remarks (e.g. authors, channel, media, URL...):

<https://superwomeninscience.wordpress.com/2018/02/08/elevator-science-part-1/>

Symposia and meetings form # 2

*Required information

Name * Francesca Govoni

E-mail Address * francesca.govoni@unitelma.it

Affiliation * Unitelma Sapienza

Presentation at scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other: Maker Faire

Partner(s) involved: Unitelma Sapienza

Title of event: Maker Faire

Type of presentation: Poster, gadget, workshop

Title of presentation: tba

Authors of presentation: Piergiuseppe Morone, Enrica Imbert, Francesca Govoni

Have all authors and their organisations agreed on the proposed presentation?

Yes

Date: 01-03/12/2017

Place: Italy, Rome

Type of audience: scientists, researchers, students, general public.

Size of audience (estimated no.): More than 110,000 visitors in three days last year

Geographical coverage (World, Europe, etc.): Europe

Are EU acknowledgement and STAR-ProBio logo properly included in the presentations? Yes

Website: <http://www.makerfairerome.eu/en/>

STAR-ProBio Symposia and meetings form # 3

*Required information

Name * Francesca Govoni

E-mail Address * francesca.govoni@unitelma.it

Affiliation * Unitelma

Presentation at scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other: Stakeholder Forum

Organisation of scientific symposia

Conference

Meeting

Workshop

Other:

Other type of activity

Organisation of training course

Direct interactions with stakeholders

Other:

Partner(s) involved: Unitelma and SQ Consult

Title of event: BBI JU Stakeholder Forum 2017

Type of presentation: PowerPoint presentation, poster and gadgets

Title of presentation: Piergiuseppe Morone presented STAR-ProBio to the audience

Authors of presentation: Piergiuseppe Morone

Have all authors and their organisations agreed on the proposed presentation?

Yes

Date: 06-07/12/2017

Place: Brussels

Type of audience: Coordinators of European projects (BBI JU and Horizon 2020),

Officers of the European Commission and Stakeholders

Size of audience (estimated no.): More than 600 participants

Are EU acknowledgements and logo (see Annex 2 of Communication and

Dissemination Strategy) and STAR-ProBio logo properly included in the

presentations? Yes

Appendix: Full report on outcomes of the first annual workshop
